

Optimization of a drinking water treatment plant operation via sequential linear programming

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ABSTRACT

The paper focuses on the operation of a drinking water treatment plant (DWTP) represented as a sequence of general reaction volumes modelled with a detailed physicochemical model. Its cost-efficient operational profile in accordance with all quality constraints at the plant output is determined by solving a sequential linear program (SLP) covering a full-day time-window. The paper provides a detailed description of the cost function and all relevant constraints used to optimize DWTP operations. To validate the approach, a simulation scenario is created using realistic parameters from a DWTP in a city in Spain. The results are compared to the plant's conventional recipe-based operation, demonstrating the potential of the proposed approach to significantly reduce operational costs. In the case study, the SLP optimization procedure achieves a 45% reduction in total costs compared to the baseline, while fully satisfying all DWTP constraints, including strict water quality requirements. The performance indicators of the derived procedure and computation complexity show a clear potential for its usage in decision support for plant operators and future extension towards model predictive control of DWTPs.

1. Introduction

In drinking water treatment plants (DWTPs) raw water abstracted from the environment (rivers, lakes, underground sources) is conditioned through a sequence of chemical and physical treatments to finally obtain drinking water, i.e. water ready for human use that then enters the water distribution system (WDS). Raw water composition or quality may vary significantly with time and this especially becomes pronounced with more frequent weather extremes which is evidenced within the observed climate change in many parts of the world. On the other hand the requirements on drinking water quality are regulated by law [1] and should be strictly respected in DWTP operation for maintaining public health and safety.

This situation makes the production of drinking water highly demanding. The DWTPs operators thus far often rely on steady-state recipes regarding dosage of chemicals in different plant reaction volumes with respect to inlet raw water quality and quantity. In the increasingly dynamical operation conditions they should receive additional support for a more resilient water service. E.g., keeping the correct pH value in intermediate steps of water treatment is important for effective usage of the applied chemicals, and also it is necessary for regulatory compliance to keep the correct pH value continuously at

the output of the plant. As pH behaviour is very nonlinear, in specific dynamic changes of raw water quality it is very hard to keep DWTP running both efficiently and in regulatory compliance. One immediate solution is to implement a decision-support system in order to advise operators on how to dose chemicals in different stages of the water treatment in dynamic conditions.

1.1. Management of individual segments of a DWTP

In this paper under the term DWTP a treatment process is considered that consists of the following water treatment steps:

1. Pre-oxidation for removing specific metals and pH value regulation.
2. Coagulation followed by flocculation, sedimentation and filtering.
3. Disinfectant dosing and pH value regulation.

These treatments are performed in several reaction volumes where water is mixed with specific chemicals and a combination of chemical and mechanical treatment takes place. Specific DWTPs may have more

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simple structure when raw water abstracted from the environment is of sufficient quality — e.g. some require only coagulation and disinfectant dosing and sometimes when high-quality ground water is abstracted only disinfectant dosing may be sufficient. In the field of DWTP operation optimization, most research focuses primarily on a single reaction volume, i.e. processes such as disinfectant or coagulant dosing. In [2], a model was developed using both a standalone random forest (RF) algorithm and a hybrid RF algorithm enhanced with a genetic algorithm (GA), called GA-RF, to assess the needed coagulant dosage to counteract changes in the raw water composition. In [3], equations for predicting the concentration of the residual aluminium were obtained using the gene expression method. The latter approaches require careful parameter tuning and computational resources to prevent overfitting or too early convergence. In [4,5], model predictive control (MPC) of the DWTP ozone dosing process is proposed. The primary shortcoming of these studies is their focus on optimizing only a single process, specifically ozone dosing. The authors in [6] presented nonlinear model predictive control for the coagulation chemical dosing unit in water treatment plants. Once again, the main disadvantage here is that only coagulation is considered neglecting other processes and chemical reactions. A composite control scheme that integrates a disturbance observer (DOB) with model predictive control (MPC) is proposed in [7] to address fluctuations in water quality while maintaining a free chlorine residual at the clear-water reservoir outlet within regulatory limits. The physicochemical model and the effects of chemical compounds within the reaction volume are not taken into consideration here. In [8], the dynamics of dissolved organic matter was investigated in enhanced coagulation, again disregarding the impact of other chemical processes present in a DWTP. The framework of Mixed Logical Dynamical (MLD) systems [9] is used for modelling, and mixed-integer programming based on this model is applied for optimizing DWTP operation, but it focuses only on coagulant dosage and filtration while considering only effluent turbidity and pH value [10]. An additional drawback is the execution time. Considerable research effort is focused on developing coagulant dosage prediction in the water treatment process using artificial neural networks (ANNs) [11]. The primary drawback of using ANNs is the need for a large amount of process data to tune its parameters properly. A precise coagulant dosing system based on a coagulation reaction model has been proposed to improve the efficiency and sustainability of water treatment processes [12]. The system considers the physical and chemical relationships between water quality and operational parameters, including the frequently neglected effect of mixing intensity. On-site evaluations showed significant reductions in coagulant dosage, energy use, and carbon emissions. However, the use of machine learning requires extensive and representative training data, and the model's performance may degrade when applied to water conditions not covered during training. A dissolved organic carbon (DOC)-based model was developed to enable real-time prediction of alum coagulant doses for surface water treatment [13]. The model was integrated with software referred to as mEnCo© [14] and tested across five water treatment plants, demonstrating strong correlations with both actual alum doses and estimates from the established software. This approach shows promise for online feedforward control and improved operational efficiency. However, its performance depends on the availability and accuracy of high-quality DOC input data, and the model may be less reliable under uncharacterized or highly variable water conditions.

1.2. Management of the entire plant

The optimization of a conventional water treatment plant using dynamic programming is presented in [15] where dynamic programming is used such that static recipes for treatment are computed by starting from the last reaction volume and then propagating back to the first one. The advantages of this work are that the whole plant is considered and that the annual costs are reduced by about 10% taking

into account the limits of the variables. Furthermore, only static models of the processes were taken into account, which is the main drawback of this work, and therefore the output of individual processes cannot be predicted based on control inputs.

There is a lack of systematic approaches for predictive control of the entire DWTP with its dynamic behaviour systematically taken into account. This article aims to address this gap by providing dynamic decision-support for DWTPs consisting of a sequence of reaction volumes, through the use of optimization based on a detailed nonlinear model of the entire DWTP.

In this paper, a dynamic physicochemical model for the general reaction volume introduced in [16] is used. The entire DWTP is considered, represented with a sequence of general reaction volumes. Grey-box model based on mass balance first principles and a set of dominant chemical reactions occurring in the reaction volumes is used. Only a small number of parameters needs adjustment to adapt for a specific real DWTP, in contrast to the use of artificial neural networks in other studies [17]. A unique building block, based on a set of chemical reactions and chemicals, is presented for use in a DWTP, allowing the approach to be easily replicated for other types of DWTPs with similar treatment processes. The approach is based on the simulation of the full DWTP nonlinear model on a prediction horizon, using a numerical integration method to obtain the response of the system represented with a set of differential equations. Through simulation, a sequence of operating points along the prediction horizon is obtained around which the DWTP nonlinear model is then linearized. The obtained sequence of linear models over time is used to formulate a linear program (LP) aimed at improving DWTP operation by optimizing perturbations of DWTP commands. Around the perturbed and improved response, these steps are repeatedly applied in a sequential linear program (SLP) procedure. The presented modelling method is applicable for different DWTPs and general reaction volumes if the considered processes and chemical reactions are known. The approach is validated through a simulation scenario of a DWTP in a Spanish city, using realistic model parameters and actual prices for the dosed chemicals.

The article provides the following contributions:

- Detailed physicochemical model of a general DWTP reaction volume effectively applied in plant optimization.
- Sequential linear program for optimized daily operation schedule of the entire DWTP.
- Verification on actual DWTP model, with demonstrated substantial economical gains in operation and computation times viable for receding horizon control implementation.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes a mathematical model of the DWTP used for the subsequent optimization procedure described in Section 3. Section 4 describes the SLP for DWTP optimization. Comparison of the optimized and traditional recipe-based daily operations for a real DWTP is reported in Section 5. Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Mathematical model of the DWTP

The DWTP considered in this research is a conventional water treatment process, enhanced with pre-oxidation processes, control of metals and total organic carbon (TOC). Its more in detail description and modelling, together with the experimental model validation, are given in [16]. In a simplified and structured way, it consists of four reaction volumes (RVs) as shown in Fig. 1. In the first reaction volume (RV1), pre-oxidation processes occur with help of the injected reagent potassium permanganate (KMnO_4), and also lime (Ca(OH)_2) is added to regulate the pH value. Dissolved chlorine gas (Cl_2) is added in the second reaction volume (RV2) to reduce the concentration of iron (Fe^{2+}) and manganese (Mn^{2+}). In the third reaction volume (RV3), coagulation/flocculation processes take place by adding the reagent

Fig. 1. Scheme of the considered DWTP [16].

aluminium sulphate ($\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$) to reduce the total organic carbon concentration. Sedimentation and filtering processes take place as well in RV3. Finally, dissolved chlorine gas and lime are added in the fourth reaction volume (RV4). The optional addition of chlorine gas keeps the free chlorine on the desired level before entering the WDS while the addition of lime raises the pH to the required value.

In this research, an important grey-box assumption is that all chemical reactions that take place in a DWTP are performed instantaneously when all reactants are present, in the amount dictated by the scarcest reactant that vanishes. The only exception is the chlorine decay process which lasts through multiple discrete-time instances and thus must be modelled with a specific finite chemical reaction speed. Furthermore, Completely Stirred Tank Reactor (CSTR) model is assumed such that there is no spatial change in concentrations of chemicals within the reaction volumes. The dynamic DWTP model consists of a series of generalized reaction volumes where the water volume in each can be fixed or varying. The modelling of chemical reactions is described in detail in [16], and for the purposes of the DWTP operation optimization, its most important constituents are explained in the sequel.

2.1. General reaction volume model

The considered concentrations of chemical elements in each RV expressed in $\left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{L}}\right)$ are: manganese $[\text{Mn}^{2+}]$, iron $[\text{Fe}^{2+}]$, equivalent carbonic acid $[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]_{\text{eq}}$, equivalent magnesium $[\text{Mg}^{2+}]_{\text{eq}}$, equivalent calcium $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{eq}}$, total organic carbon [TOC], sulphate $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$, total free chlorine $[\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}}$, permanganate $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$, potassium $[\text{K}^+]$, chloride ion $[\text{Cl}^-]$, equivalent aluminium $[\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{eq}}$, hydrogen ion $[\text{H}^+]$ and hydroxide ion $[\text{OH}^-]$. Further, all of the concentrations in the index marked by the letters 'eq' represent the total concentration of all species of that element, which are in a certain balance, and cause a reaction as long as the total concentration is larger than zero since due to the balance established this implies that also the reacting species is present [16]. The following chemical reactions are considered for each RV:

where the arrow pointing downwards \downarrow to the right of a chemical compound represents a precipitate of the chemical reaction while '(g)' next to a chemical annotates that the specific chemical is in the gaseous phase.

In the following the subscript 'prv' is used with the meaning 'previous reaction volume', such that q_{prv} is the output water flow from the previous reaction volume while $[X]_{\text{prv}}$ is the concentration of the chemical X in that output flow — due to fast mixing assumed in each reaction volume it corresponds to the concentration of X in the previous

reaction volume. For presentation clarity, the following substitutions are introduced:

$$[\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{eq,in}} = K_{\text{S0}}[\text{H}^+]^3_{\text{prv}} + K_{\text{S1}}[\text{H}^+]^2_{\text{prv}} + K_{\text{S2}}[\text{H}^+]_{\text{prv}} + K_{\text{S3}} + \frac{K_{\text{S4}}}{[\text{H}^+]_{\text{prv}}}, \quad (6)$$

$$\{\text{MnO}_4^-\}_{\text{in,total}} = q_{\text{prv}} \cdot [\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{prv}} + q_{\text{KMnO}_4} \cdot [\text{KMnO}_4]_{\text{in}}, \quad (7)$$

$$\{\text{K}^+\}_{\text{in,total}} = q_{\text{prv}} \cdot [\text{K}^+]_{\text{prv}} + q_{\text{KMnO}_4} \cdot [\text{KMnO}_4]_{\text{in}}, \quad (8)$$

$$\{\text{Cl}^-\}_{\text{in,total}} = q_{\text{prv}} \cdot [\text{Cl}^-]_{\text{prv}} + q_{\text{Cl}_2} \cdot [\text{Cl}_2]_{\text{in}}, \quad (9)$$

$$\{\text{HOCl}\}_{\text{eq,in,total}} = q_{\text{prv}} \cdot [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq,prv}} + q_{\text{Cl}_2} \cdot [\text{Cl}_2]_{\text{in}}, \quad (10)$$

$$\{\text{Ca}^{2+}\}_{\text{eq,in,total}} = q_{\text{prv}} \cdot [\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{eq,prv}} + q_{\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2} \cdot [\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2]_{\text{in}}, \quad (11)$$

$$\{\text{Al}^{3+}\}_{\text{eq,in,total}} = q_{\text{prv}} \cdot [\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{eq,prv}} + 2 \cdot q_{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3} \cdot [\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3]_{\text{in}} - (q_{\text{prv}} + 2 \cdot q_{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3}) \cdot \frac{\text{DOSE}}{1000}, \quad (12)$$

$$\{\text{SO}_4^{2-}\}_{\text{in,total}} = q_{\text{prv}} \cdot [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{prv}} + 3 \cdot q_{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3} \cdot [\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3]_{\text{in}}, \quad (13)$$

$$q_{\text{in,total}} = q_{\text{prv}} + q_{\text{KMnO}_4} + q_{\text{Cl}_2} + q_{\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2} + q_{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3}, \quad (14)$$

$$\text{DOSE} = \max \left(0; \frac{q_{\text{prv}} \cdot [\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{eq,prv}} + 2 \cdot q_{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3} \cdot [\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3]_{\text{in}}}{q_{\text{prv}} + 2 \cdot q_{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3}} - [\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{eq,in}} \right) \cdot 1000, \quad (15)$$

where the constants $K_{\text{S0}}-K_{\text{S4}}$ represent the solubility constants. The subscript 'in' in $[X]_{\text{in}} \left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{L}}\right)$ denotes the concentration of the chemical compound X that is dissolved in its corresponding input stream into the reaction volume, while $q_{\text{prv}} \left(\frac{\text{L}}{\text{s}}\right)$ and $q_X \left(\frac{\text{L}}{\text{s}}\right)$ denote the flow from the previous reaction volume and flow of input water in which the corresponding reagent 'X' is dissolved, respectively. The annotation $\{\dot{X}\} \left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{s}}\right)$ represents the molar rate input into the reaction volume of the chemical compound X. Furthermore, the subscript 'total' represents the combined contribution of the dosed solutions and of the previous reaction volume. The variable $\text{DOSE} \left(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{L}}\right)$ represents the coagulant dose, i.e. the concentration of aluminium hydroxide ($\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$) crystal structures which are formed by the addition of aluminium sulphate and which serve to fetch and precipitate the adsorbable fraction of organic carbon. For easier following and referencing, all annotations are listed and explained once more in [Appendix](#).

The differential equations of the concentrations are introduced as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[\text{MnO}_4^-]}{dt} = & \frac{1}{V} \left(\max \left(0; \{\text{MnO}_4^-\}_{\text{in,total}} - \frac{1}{3}[\text{Fe}^{2+}]_{\text{in}} \cdot q_{\text{prv}} - \frac{2}{3}[\text{Mn}^{2+}]_{\text{in}} \cdot q_{\text{prv}} \right) \right. \\ & \left. - q_{\text{in,total}} \cdot [\text{MnO}_4^-] \right) \\ & - \frac{1}{3}[\text{Fe}^{2+}] \cdot \delta(f_2([\text{Fe}^{2+}], [\text{MnO}_4^-])) \\ & - \frac{2}{3}[\text{Mn}^{2+}] \cdot \delta(f_2([\text{Mn}^{2+}], [\text{MnO}_4^-])), \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where δ is the Dirac delta function, while the function f_n is defined as:

$$f_n(\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \dots, \zeta_n) = \begin{cases} \neq 0 & \text{if any } \zeta_i \leq 0 \\ 0 & \text{if all } \zeta_i > 0. \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Eq. (16) describes a rapid chemical reaction at the inlet of the RV, a rapid chemical reaction within the RV, and liquid mixing. The chemical reactions at both the inlet and inside the RV occur instantaneously whenever all reactants are present, proceeding in amounts limited by the scarcest reactant, which is completely consumed. The only exception is active chlorine decay which is modelled with a specific decay rate. The remaining differential equations, structured in an analogous way, are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[\text{Cl}^-]}{dt} = & \frac{1}{V} \left(\{ \text{Cl}^- \}_{\text{in,total}} + \min \left(\frac{1}{1} \cdot [\text{Mn}^{2+}]_{\text{in}} \cdot q_{\text{prv}}; \{ \text{HOCl} \}_{\text{eq,in,total}} \right) \right. \\ & \left. + \min \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot [\text{Fe}^{2+}]_{\text{in}} \cdot q_{\text{prv}}; \{ \text{HOCl} \}_{\text{eq,in,total}} \right) \right. \\ & \left. - q_{\text{in,total}} \cdot [\text{Cl}^-] \right) + \min \left(\frac{1}{1} [\text{Mn}^{2+}]; \frac{1}{1} [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}} \right) \\ & \cdot \delta(f_2([\text{Mn}^{2+}], [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}})) \\ & + \min \left(\frac{1}{1} [\text{Fe}^{2+}]; \frac{1}{1} [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}} \right) \cdot \delta(f_2([\text{Fe}^{2+}], [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}})) \\ & + k_d [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}}, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}}}{dt} = & \frac{1}{V} \left(\max \left(0; \{ \text{HOCl} \}_{\text{eq,in,total}} - \frac{1}{1} [\text{Mn}^{2+}]_{\text{in}} \cdot q_{\text{prv}} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - \frac{1}{2} [\text{Fe}^{2+}]_{\text{in}} \cdot q_{\text{prv}} \right) - q_{\text{in,total}} \cdot [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}} \right) \\ & - \frac{1}{1} [\text{Mn}^{2+}] \cdot \delta(f_2([\text{Mn}^{2+}], [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}})) \\ & - \frac{1}{2} [\text{Fe}^{2+}] \cdot \delta(f_2([\text{Fe}^{2+}], [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}})) - k_d \cdot [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[\text{Mn}^{2+}]}{dt} = & \frac{1}{V} \left(\max \left(0; [\text{Mn}^{2+}]_{\text{in}} \cdot q_{\text{prv}} - \frac{1}{1} \{ \text{HOCl} \}_{\text{eq,in,total}} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - \frac{3}{2} \{ \text{MnO}_4^- \}_{\text{in,total}} \right) - q_{\text{in,total}} \cdot [\text{Mn}^{2+}] \right) \\ & - \frac{1}{1} [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}} \cdot \delta(f_2([\text{Mn}^{2+}], [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}})) \\ & - \frac{3}{2} [\text{MnO}_4^-] \cdot \delta(f_2([\text{Mn}^{2+}], [\text{MnO}_4^-])), \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[\text{Fe}^{2+}]}{dt} = & \frac{1}{V} \left(\max \left(0; [\text{Fe}^{2+}]_{\text{in}} \cdot q_{\text{prv}} - \frac{2}{1} \{ \text{HOCl} \}_{\text{eq,in,total}} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - \frac{3}{1} \{ \text{MnO}_4^- \}_{\text{in,total}} \right) - q_{\text{in,total}} \cdot [\text{Fe}^{2+}] \right) \\ & - \frac{2}{1} [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}} \cdot \delta(f_2([\text{Fe}^{2+}], [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}})) \\ & - \frac{3}{1} [\text{MnO}_4^-] \cdot \delta(f_2([\text{Fe}^{2+}], [\text{MnO}_4^-])), \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{d[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{eq}}}{dt} = \frac{1}{V} \left(\{ \text{Ca}^{2+} \}_{\text{eq,in,total}} - q_{\text{in,total}} \cdot [\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{eq}} \right), \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{d[\text{Mg}^{2+}]_{\text{eq}}}{dt} = \frac{1}{V} \left([\text{Mg}^{2+}]_{\text{eq,in}} \cdot q_{\text{prv}} - q_{\text{in,total}} \cdot [\text{Mg}^{2+}]_{\text{eq}} \right), \quad (23)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]_{\text{eq}}}{dt} = & \frac{1}{V} \left(\max \left(0; [\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]_{\text{eq,in}} \cdot q_{\text{prv}} - \frac{3}{1} \cdot q_{\text{in,total}} \cdot \text{DOSE} \right) \right. \\ & \left. - q_{\text{in,total}} \cdot [\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]_{\text{eq}} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{d[\text{K}^+]}{dt} = \frac{1}{V} \left(\{ \text{K}^+ \}_{\text{in,total}} - q_{\text{in,total}} \cdot [\text{K}^+] \right), \quad (25)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[\text{TOC}]}{dt} = & \frac{1}{V} \left(h \left(K_1, K_2, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, b_{\text{langmuir}}, \text{DOSE}, \text{pH}, [\text{TOC}]_{\text{in}} \right) \right. \\ & \left. \cdot \frac{q_{\text{prv}}}{q_{\text{in,total}}} \right) \cdot q_{\text{in,total}} - q_{\text{in,total}} \cdot [\text{TOC}], \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{d[\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{eq}}}{dt} = \frac{1}{V} \left(\{ \text{Al}^{3+} \}_{\text{eq,in,total}} - q_{\text{in,total}} \cdot [\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{eq}} \right), \quad (27)$$

$$\frac{d[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{dt} = \frac{1}{V} \left(\{ \text{SO}_4^{2-} \}_{\text{in,total}} - q_{\text{in,total}} \cdot [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] \right), \quad (28)$$

where k_d denotes the chlorine decay constant, V is the amount of the reaction volume, h represents the function of Edwards model for quantification of remaining TOC after its capture with the coagulant crystals in the input stream [16] — the crystals subsequently form flocks which are then sedimented or filtered, while $K_1, K_2, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ and b_{langmuir} represent the semi-empirical coefficients.

The output of the model is the pH value established at the reaction volume. It is modelled by starting with the dissociation equation for water:

$$[\text{H}^+] \cdot [\text{OH}^-] = k_w = 10^{-14} \left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{L}} \right)^2. \quad (29)$$

Furthermore, from the charge balance follows:

$$[\text{H}^+] - [\text{OH}^-] = r_{\text{net}}, \quad (30)$$

where r_{net} is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} r_{\text{net}} = & [\text{HCO}_3^-]([\text{H}^+], [\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]_{\text{eq}}) + 2[\text{CO}_3^{2-}]([\text{H}^+], [\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]_{\text{eq}}) \\ & + [\text{Cl}^-] + [\text{MnO}_4^-] + 2[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] \\ & + [\text{ClO}^-]([\text{H}^+], [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}}) - 2[\text{Ca}^{2+}]([\text{H}^+], [\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{eq}}) \\ & - 2[\text{Mg}^{2+}]([\text{H}^+], [\text{Mg}^{2+}]_{\text{eq}}) - 2[\text{Fe}^{2+}] \\ & - 2[\text{Mn}^{2+}] - [\text{K}^+] - [\text{CaOH}^+]([\text{H}^+], [\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{eq}}) \\ & - [\text{MgOH}^+]([\text{H}^+], [\text{Mg}^{2+}]_{\text{eq}}) - c_{\text{avg}}[\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{eq}}, \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

where the functions of dependence on the concentrations of chemical compounds whose dynamics are considered are described in [16]. The constant $c_{\text{avg}} = -0.1937$ denotes the average charge of the dissolved aluminium species at pH value 7 to simplify the calculation. By combining the expressions (29), (30) and (31) one gets the equation for $[\text{H}^+]$ with a ninth order polynomial equated to 0 which is not written here because of the length of its notation. From the solution of this equation, the pH value is calculated as follows:

$$\text{pH} = -\log[\text{H}^+]. \quad (32)$$

2.2. DWTP state-space model

The nonlinear state-space model of the DWTP is described by collecting differential Eqs. (16)–(28) across all four reaction volumes and Eqs. (29)–(32) for computing pH in all four reaction volumes, as follows:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = f_c(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{d}), \quad (33)$$

where the system states $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ are the concentrations of the chemical elements in the reaction volumes:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_n = \begin{bmatrix} [\text{MnO}_4^-]_n, [\text{Cl}^-]_n, [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq},n}, [\text{Mn}^{2+}]_n, [\text{Fe}^{2+}]_n, [\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{eq},n}, \\ [\text{Mg}^{2+}]_{\text{eq},n}, [\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]_{\text{eq},n}, [\text{K}^+]_n, [\text{TOC}]_n, [\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{eq},n}, [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_n \end{bmatrix}^T, \quad (34)$$

$$\mathbf{x} = \left[\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_1^T, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_2^T, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{N_{\text{RV}}}^T \right]^T, \quad (35)$$

where $n \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{RV}}$ and $\mathcal{N}_{\text{RV}} = \{1, 2, \dots, N_{\text{RV}}\}$ is the set of indices of reaction volumes and $N_{\text{RV}} = 4$ is the total number of reaction volumes in the considered DWTP. Here N_{RV} is fixed to 4, to relate to the concrete DWTP considered, but the generality of the approach for an arbitrary number of reaction volumes in a sequence remains. The symbol tilde \sim above a variable indicates that the variable is associated exclusively to the n th reaction volume. The control inputs gathered in vector $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ are the input flows of prepared solutions of chemicals as follows:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_1 = [q_{\text{KMnO}_4}, q_{\text{Ca(OH)}_2, \text{RV1}}]^T, \quad (36)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_2 = q_{\text{Cl}_2, \text{RV2}}, \quad (37)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_3 = q_{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3}, \quad (38)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_4 = [q_{\text{Ca(OH)}_2, \text{RV4}}, q_{\text{Cl}_2, \text{RV4}}]^T, \quad (39)$$

Table 1
Raw water quality. The concentrations are expressed in mg/L.

$[\text{Mn}^{2+}]_{\text{raw}}$	$[\text{Fe}^{2+}]_{\text{raw}}$	$[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{eq,raw}}$	$[\text{Mg}^{2+}]_{\text{eq,raw}}$	$[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]_{\text{eq}}$	[TOC]
0.543	0.308	30	4.5	175	6.12

Table 2
Doses of each reagent. The reagent dosages are expressed in L/s.

	RV1	RV2	RV3	RV4
q_{KMnO_4}	0.013	–	–	–
$q_{\text{Ca(OH)}_2}$	0.98	–	–	2.673
q_{Cl_2}	–	0.85	–	0.125
$q_{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3}$	–	–	0.024	–

Table 3
Comparison of measurements to the model results. The concentrations are expressed in mg/L.

	$[\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}}$	$[\text{Fe}^{2+}]$	$[\text{Mn}^{2+}]$	[TOC]	pH
Measurement	1.1	0	0.009	1.63	7.3
Model	1.1	0	0	1.64	7.3

Table 4
RMSE and MAE values for each corresponding chemical compound.

	$[\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq}}$	$[\text{Fe}^{2+}]$	$[\text{Mn}^{2+}]$	[TOC]	pH
RMSE	0.0329	0	0.0010	0.0440	0.0020
MAE	0.1380	0	0.0270	0.1480	0.0200

$$\mathbf{u} = \left[\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_1^T, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_2^T, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{N_{\text{RV}}}^T \right]^T. \quad (40)$$

The system disturbance inputs $\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_d}$ are concentrations of raw water elements at the inlet to the first reaction volume, and water intake into the WDS:

$$\mathbf{d} = \left[\begin{array}{c} [\text{Mn}^{2+}]_{\text{raw}}, [\text{Fe}^{2+}]_{\text{raw}}, [\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]_{\text{eq,raw}}, [\text{Mg}^{2+}]_{\text{eq,raw}}, [\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{eq,raw}}, [\text{TOC}]_{\text{raw}}, [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{\text{raw}}, \\ [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq,raw}}, [\text{MnO}_4^-]_{\text{raw}}, [\text{K}^+]_{\text{raw}}, [\text{Cl}^-]_{\text{raw}}, [\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{raw}}, q_{\text{DWTP,WDS}} \end{array} \right]^T, \quad (41)$$

where $q_{\text{DWTP,WDS}}$ is the flow of treated water from the DWTP to the WDS. Finally, $f_c : \mathbb{R}^{n_x} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_u} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_d} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ is a general nonlinear vector function. In the case of the considered DWTP, the system outputs $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ can be represented as a static function of state, controllable and disturbance inputs:

$$\mathbf{y} = g(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{d}), \quad (42)$$

where $g : \mathbb{R}^{n_x} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_u} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_d} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ is a nonlinear vector function. The system outputs are the concentrations of the chemical elements at the outlet of the n th reaction volume as well as the pH value in it:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_n = \left[\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_n^T, \text{pH}_n \right]^T, \quad (43)$$

$$\mathbf{y} = \left[\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_1^T, \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_2^T, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{N_{\text{RV}}}^T \right]^T. \quad (44)$$

The corresponding concentrations in the n th reaction volume can be expressed using the vector of system states as:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_n = \mathbf{H}_n \cdot \mathbf{x}, \quad (45)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_n \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{x,n} \times n_x}$ represents the selection matrix. The control inputs in the n th reaction volume can similarly be represented by the control input vector as follows:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_n = \mathbf{G}_n \cdot \mathbf{u}, \quad (46)$$

where $\mathbf{G}_n \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{u,n} \times n_u}$ represents the selection matrix. In the case of RV1, $[\text{X}]_{\text{prv}}$ and q_{prv} are $[\text{X}]_{\text{raw}}$ and q_{raw} while q_{raw} is defined as

$$q_{\text{raw}} = q_{\text{DWTP,WDS}} - (q_{\text{KMnO}_4} + q_{\text{Ca(OH)}_2, \text{RV1}} + q_{\text{Cl}_2, \text{RV2}} + q_{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3} + q_{\text{Ca(OH)}_2, \text{RV4}} + q_{\text{Cl}_2, \text{RV4}}). \quad (47)$$

2.3. Validation of the DWTP model

Empirical data from an actual DWTP are used in [16] to confirm a satisfactory model accuracy. Here only the key information related to model validation from the referenced article is extracted. One specific static plant inputs taken from the plant operation log for validation are as follows in Tables 1 and 2, which show the raw water quality and the doses of each reagent, respectively. The raw water quality and the doses of each reagent were constant throughout the day in the model, driven by the average daily recorded flow from DWTP to WDS. Table 3 compares the measurements taken at the DWTP's output, i.e. at the fourth reaction volume's output, to the values calculated using the proposed model for the known input raw water quality, fresh water demand and chemicals dosages applied. Table 3 presents the results for a single static set of measurements. In addition, RMSE and MAE values, as systematic error indicators, were calculated using five static sets of measurements obtained from plant data logs to further demonstrate the model's accuracy, and the results are shown in Table 4.

In this study, the Edwards model parameters adopted from the literature [18], along with the chlorine decay constant, were further tuned. The values of RMSE and MAE from Table 4 indicate a satisfactory model accuracy.

3. DWTP optimization

For computer-based decision-making and optimization, the behaviour of a continuous-time system is represented through variables samples taken at discrete-time instants. They are equidistant in time and this distance, the sampling time, is denoted with T . The values of time variables $\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{d}$ or \mathbf{y} at a specific time kT that is an integer multiple of the sampling time, i.e. $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ are denoted with $\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{d}_k$ and \mathbf{y}_k , respectively. Under the assumption of constant inputs \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{d} between the sampling instants, that is in time period

$$\mathcal{T}_k = [kT, (k+1)T), \quad (48)$$

the nonlinear continuous-time dynamics represented with f_c in (33) is discretized

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = f_d(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{d}_k), \quad (49)$$

where $f_d : \mathbb{R}^{n_x} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_u} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_d} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, while \mathbf{x}_k and \mathbf{u}_k are defined as:

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{1,k}^T, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{2,k}^T, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{N_{RV},k}^T \end{bmatrix}^T, \quad (50)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{1,k}^T, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{2,k}^T, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{N_{RV},k}^T \end{bmatrix}^T. \quad (51)$$

3.1. Linearization and discretization of the continuous-time DWTP model

The explanation of the procedure to obtain a discrete-time linearized DWTP model starts with linearization and time discretization of a system of differential equations for a chemical reaction of reactants A and B dissolved in a solution in a reaction volume of size V . Let the chemical reaction be represented by

where a and b are stoichiometric coefficients. The corresponding system of differential equations is:

$$V \frac{d[A]}{dt} = \max \left(0; q_{A_{in}} [A]_{in} - \frac{a}{b} q_{B_{in}} [B]_{in} \right) - (q_{A_{in}} + q_{B_{in}}) [A] - V \frac{a}{b} [B] \cdot \delta(f_2([A], [B])), \quad (53)$$

$$V \frac{d[B]}{dt} = \max \left(0; q_{B_{in}} [B]_{in} - \frac{b}{a} q_{A_{in}} [A]_{in} \right) - (q_{A_{in}} + q_{B_{in}}) [B] - V \frac{b}{a} [A] \cdot \delta(f_2([A], [B])), \quad (54)$$

where $q_{A_{in}}$ and $q_{B_{in}}$ are inflows into the reaction volume of solutions that carry dissolved substances A and B, respectively. It is assumed that A and B react instantaneously when both are present, in the amount dictated by the scarcer reactant which then vanishes. For this reason, additional constraints apply depending on whether both reactants are present for the chemical reaction to occur at the entrance into the reaction volume where input flows mix, and within the reaction volume. Since Eqs. (53) and (54) contain max function and discontinuous functions f_2 , there are twelve possible combinations of constraints to enumerate all possible activations of discontinued parts of these functions at the discrete-time instant k , as follows:

- (53).a

$$\left(q_{A_{in},k} [A]_{in,k} - \frac{a}{b} q_{B_{in},k} [B]_{in,k} \right) \geq 0, [A]_k \geq 0, [B]_k \geq 0, \quad (55)$$

- (53).b

$$\left(q_{A_{in},k} [A]_{in,k} - \frac{a}{b} q_{B_{in},k} [B]_{in,k} \right) \geq 0, [A]_k \leq 0, [B]_k \geq 0, \quad (56)$$

- (53).c

$$\left(q_{A_{in},k} [A]_{in,k} - \frac{a}{b} q_{B_{in},k} [B]_{in,k} \right) \geq 0, [A]_k \geq 0, [B]_k \leq 0, \quad (57)$$

- (53).d

$$\left(q_{A_{in},k} [A]_{in,k} - \frac{a}{b} q_{B_{in},k} [B]_{in,k} \right) \leq 0, [A]_k \geq 0, [B]_k \geq 0, \quad (58)$$

- (53).e

$$\left(q_{A_{in},k} [A]_{in,k} - \frac{a}{b} q_{B_{in},k} [B]_{in,k} \right) \leq 0, [A]_k \leq 0, [B]_k \geq 0, \quad (59)$$

- (53).f

$$\left(q_{A_{in},k} [A]_{in,k} - \frac{a}{b} q_{B_{in},k} [B]_{in,k} \right) \leq 0, [A]_k \geq 0, [B]_k \leq 0, \quad (60)$$

- (54).a

$$\left(q_{B_{in},k} [B]_{in,k} - \frac{b}{a} q_{A_{in},k} [A]_{in,k} \right) \geq 0, [A]_k \geq 0, [B]_k \geq 0, \quad (61)$$

- (54).b

$$\left(q_{B_{in},k} [B]_{in,k} - \frac{b}{a} q_{A_{in},k} [A]_{in,k} \right) \geq 0, [A]_k \leq 0, [B]_k \geq 0, \quad (62)$$

- (54).c

$$\left(q_{B_{in},k} [B]_{in,k} - \frac{b}{a} q_{A_{in},k} [A]_{in,k} \right) \geq 0, [A]_k \geq 0, [B]_k \leq 0, \quad (63)$$

- (54).d

$$\left(q_{B_{in},k} [B]_{in,k} - \frac{b}{a} q_{A_{in},k} [A]_{in,k} \right) \leq 0, [A]_k \geq 0, [B]_k \geq 0, \quad (64)$$

- (54).e

$$\left(q_{B_{in},k} [B]_{in,k} - \frac{b}{a} q_{A_{in},k} [A]_{in,k} \right) \leq 0, [A]_k \leq 0, [B]_k \geq 0, \quad (65)$$

- (54).f

$$\left(q_{B_{in},k} [B]_{in,k} - \frac{b}{a} q_{A_{in},k} [A]_{in,k} \right) \leq 0, [A]_k \geq 0, [B]_k \leq 0. \quad (66)$$

The listed constraints (53) and (54), when intersected, define regions in the space formed by variables $[A]_k$, $[B]_k$, $[A]_{in,k}$, $[B]_{in,k}$, $q_{A_{in},k}$ and $q_{B_{in},k}$. In each region a specific mapping holds for concentrations $[A]_k$ and $[B]_k$ between two consecutive discrete-time instants. As all the regions are closed, the regions that are not full-dimensional can be neglected since their area is already included in the full-dimensional regions. It can be seen that constraint (53).a has a lower-dimensional intersection with constraints (54).a, (54).b, (54).c, (54).e and (54).f. Furthermore, (53).b has a lower-dimensional intersection with (54).a, (54).b, (54).c, (54).d and (54).f. Constraint (53).c has a lower-dimensional intersection with (54).a, (54).b, (54).c, (54).d and (54).e. Next, (53).d has a lower-dimensional intersection with (54).b, (54).c, (54).d, (54).e and (54).f. Constraint (53).e has a lower-dimensional intersection with (54).a, (54).c, (54).d, (54).e and (54).f. Finally, (53).f has a lower-dimensional intersection with (54).a, (54).b, (54).d, (54).e and (54).f. In this way, a total of six combinations of constraints yields full-dimensional regions with a specific discrete-time mapping of concentrations in each:

1. (53).a and (54).d,
2. (53).b and (54).e,
3. (53).c and (54).f,
4. (53).d and (54).a,
5. (53).e and (54).b,
6. (53).f and (54).c.

For the continuous-time system described in (53)–(54), the corresponding time-discretized linearized system in the operating point defined with $[A]_{k,0}$, $[B]_{k,0}$, $[A]_{in,k,0}$, $[B]_{in,k,0}$, $q_{A_{in},k,0}$, $q_{B_{in},k,0}$ is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta[A]_{k+1} \\ \Delta[B]_{k+1} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{K}_{X,k,n_{con}} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta[A]_k \\ \Delta[B]_k \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{K}_{q,k,n_{con}} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta q_{A_{in},k} \\ \Delta q_{B_{in},k} \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{K}_{in,k,n_{con}} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta[A]_{in,k} \\ \Delta[B]_{in,k} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (67)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_{X,k,n_{con}}$, $\mathbf{K}_{q,k,n_{con}}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{in,k,n_{con}}$ corresponding to specific combination $n_{con} = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$, of the six previously mentioned constraints, as follows:

- (53).a and (54).d

$$\mathbf{K}_{X,k,1} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\sigma_k T} & -\frac{a}{b} \\ -\frac{b}{a} & e^{\sigma_k T} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (68)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{q,k,1} = \mathbf{M}_k \cdot \begin{bmatrix} [A]_{in,k,0} - [A]_{k,0} & -\frac{a}{b} [B]_{in,k,0} - [A]_{k,0} \\ -[B]_{k,0} & -[B]_{k,0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (69)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{in,k,1} = \mathbf{M}_k \cdot \begin{bmatrix} q_{A_{in},k,0} & -\frac{a}{b} q_{B_{in},k,0} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (70)$$

- (53).b and (54).e

$$\mathbf{K}_{X,k,2} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\sigma_k T} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{\sigma_k T} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (71)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{q,k,2} = \mathbf{M}_k \cdot \begin{bmatrix} [A]_{in,k,0} - [A]_{k,0} & -\frac{a}{b} [B]_{in,k,0} - [A]_{k,0} \\ -[B]_{k,0} & -[B]_{k,0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (72)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{\text{in},k,2} = \mathbf{M}_k \cdot \begin{bmatrix} q_{A_{\text{in}},k,0} & -\frac{a}{b}q_{B_{\text{in}},k,0} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (73)$$

• (53).d and (54).a

$$\mathbf{K}_{X,k,4} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\sigma_k T} & -\frac{a}{b} \\ -\frac{b}{a} & e^{\sigma_k T} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (74)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{q,k,4} = \mathbf{M}_k \cdot \begin{bmatrix} -[A]_{k,0} & -[A]_{k,0} \\ -\frac{b}{a}[A]_{\text{in},k,0} - [B]_{k,0} & [B]_{\text{in},k,0} - [B]_{k,0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (75)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{\text{in},k,4} = \mathbf{M}_k \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{b}{a}q_{A_{\text{in}},k,0} & q_{B_{\text{in}},k,0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (76)$$

• (53).e and (54).b

$$\mathbf{K}_{X,k,5} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{\sigma_k T} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{\sigma_k T} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (77)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{q,k,5} = \mathbf{M}_k \cdot \begin{bmatrix} -[A]_{k,0} & -[A]_{k,0} \\ -\frac{b}{a}[A]_{\text{in},k,0} - [B]_{k,0} & [B]_{\text{in},k,0} - [B]_{k,0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (78)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{\text{in},k,5} = \mathbf{M}_k \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{b}{a}q_{A_{\text{in}},k,0} & q_{B_{\text{in}},k,0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (79)$$

while \mathbf{M}_k and σ_k are defined as:

$$\mathbf{M}_k = \sigma_k \cdot \mathbf{I}_{2 \times 2} \cdot (e^{\sigma_k T \cdot \mathbf{I}_{2 \times 2}} - \mathbf{I}_{2 \times 2}), \quad (80)$$

$$\sigma_k = -\frac{q_{A_{\text{in}},k,0} + q_{B_{\text{in}},k,0}}{V}, \quad (81)$$

where $\mathbf{I}_{2 \times 2}$ denotes the identity matrix of order 2. The matrices $\mathbf{K}_{X,k,3}$, $\mathbf{K}_{q,k,3}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{\text{in},k,3}$ are equal to $\mathbf{K}_{X,k,2}$, $\mathbf{K}_{q,k,2}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{\text{in},k,2}$, respectively. Also, the matrices $\mathbf{K}_{X,k,6}$, $\mathbf{K}_{q,k,6}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{\text{in},k,6}$ are equal to $\mathbf{K}_{X,k,5}$, $\mathbf{K}_{q,k,5}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{\text{in},k,5}$, respectively. Small changes around the operating point $\Delta q_{A_{\text{in}},k}$, $\Delta q_{B_{\text{in}},k}$, $\Delta[A]_k$, $\Delta[B]_k$, $\Delta[A]_{\text{in},k}$ and $\Delta[B]_{\text{in},k}$ are defined as follows:

$$\Delta[A]_k = [A]_k - [A]_{k,0} \quad (82)$$

$$\Delta[B]_k = [B]_k - [B]_{k,0} \quad (83)$$

$$\Delta q_{A_{\text{in}},k} = q_{A_{\text{in}},k} - q_{A_{\text{in}},k,0} \quad (84)$$

$$\Delta q_{B_{\text{in}},k} = q_{B_{\text{in}},k} - q_{B_{\text{in}},k,0} \quad (85)$$

$$\Delta[A]_{\text{in},k} = [A]_{\text{in},k} - [A]_{\text{in},k,0} \quad (86)$$

$$\Delta[B]_{\text{in},k} = [B]_{\text{in},k} - [B]_{\text{in},k,0} \quad (87)$$

The procedure is analogous for all reaction volumes and their respective differential equations introduced in Section 2.1

Finally, the small change in pH value in reaction volume n at time step k around the operating point $\text{pH}_{n,k,0}$ is determined using (32), as follows:

$$\Delta \text{pH}_{n,k} = -\frac{1}{[\text{H}^+]_{k,0} \ln(10)} \Delta[\text{H}^+]_{n,k}, \quad (88)$$

where $\Delta[\text{H}^+]_{n,k}$ can be approximated with a linear function of $\Delta \mathbf{x}_k$, $\Delta \mathbf{u}_k$ and $\Delta \mathbf{d}_k$ using (29)–(31) and Taylor expansion

$$\Delta[\text{H}^+]_{n,k} = \sum_{j=1}^{n_x} \frac{\partial[\text{H}^+]_{n,k}}{\partial x_j} \Delta x_{k,j} + \sum_{j=1}^{n_u} \frac{\partial[\text{H}^+]_{n,k}}{\partial u_j} \Delta u_{k,j} + \sum_{j=1}^{n_d} \frac{\partial[\text{H}^+]_{n,k}}{\partial d_j} \Delta d_{k,j}. \quad (89)$$

After the linearization procedure, the small change in pH value in the reaction volume $n \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{RV}}$ can be expressed as follows:

$$\Delta \text{pH}_{n,k} = \mathbf{P}_n \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{x}_k \\ \Delta \mathbf{u}_k \\ \Delta \mathbf{d}_k \end{bmatrix}, \quad (90)$$

where \mathbf{P}_n is the matrix of coefficients.

3.2. DWTP operational cost and constraints

The operational cost of the considered DWTP over a specific time period consists of the cost of chemicals added during water treatment

to ensure that the water remains within the allowable concentration limits. In Spain, these limits are regulated by [19], which defines the quality parameters for water intended for human consumption at the outlet of DWTPs, as detailed in its Annex I (Parameters and parametric values). This paper considers the optimal day-ahead scheduling of the DWTP system for a specific predicted disturbance profile, with the objective of minimizing operational costs. As water is supplied to the considered DWTP by gravity, energy costs for the considered DWTP correspond only to constant consumption that does not depend on the controlled chemicals dosages or to very small consumption of dosing pumps that is neglected. Furthermore, the cost for generated sludge treatment is for this plant neglectable compared to the chemicals cost. If that would not be the case, the derived model would have to have additional outputs that model the rate of precipitates forming.

The daily operational cost function for the considered DWTP system is thus given by:

$$\begin{aligned} J = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} & \left(p_{\text{KMnO}_4} M_{\text{KMnO}_4} [\text{KMnO}_4]_{\text{in}} q_{\text{KMnO}_4,k} \right. \\ & + p_{\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2} M_{\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2} [\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2]_{\text{in}} (q_{\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2,\text{RV}1,k} + q_{\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2,\text{RV}4,k}) \\ & + p_{\text{Cl}_2} M_{\text{Cl}_2} [\text{Cl}_2]_{\text{in}} (q_{\text{Cl}_2,\text{RV}2,k} + q_{\text{Cl}_2,\text{RV}4,k}) \\ & \left. + p_{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3} M_{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3} [\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3]_{\text{in}} q_{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3,k} \right) \cdot T, \end{aligned} \quad (91)$$

where p_{KMnO_4} , $p_{\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2}$, p_{Cl_2} and $p_{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3}$ are the prices per kilogram of the potassium permanganate, lime, chlorine gas and aluminium sulphate, respectively. The constants M_{KMnO_4} , $M_{\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2}$, M_{Cl_2} and $M_{\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3}$ are the molar masses of the same chemicals, measured in kilograms per mole $\left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{mol}}\right)$. With $N \in \mathbb{N}$ length of the prediction horizon is denoted.

To ensure that the treated water exiting the DWTP meets demanding quality standards, it is important to establish stringent limits on the state variables. These variables encompass the concentrations of the components within the DWTP model. Minimum and maximum concentrations can be defined for all states in each of the reaction volumes $n \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{RV}}$:

$$[\text{Mn}^{2+}]_{n,\text{min}} \leq [\text{Mn}^{2+}]_{n,k} \leq [\text{Mn}^{2+}]_{n,\text{max}}, \quad (92)$$

$$[\text{Fe}^{2+}]_{n,\text{min}} \leq [\text{Fe}^{2+}]_{n,k} \leq [\text{Fe}^{2+}]_{n,\text{max}}, \quad (93)$$

$$[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]_{\text{eq},n,\text{min}} \leq [\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]_{\text{eq},n,k} \leq [\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]_{\text{eq},n,\text{max}}, \quad (94)$$

$$[\text{Mg}^{2+}]_{\text{eq},n,\text{min}} \leq [\text{Mg}^{2+}]_{\text{eq},n,k} \leq [\text{Mg}^{2+}]_{\text{eq},n,\text{max}}, \quad (95)$$

$$[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{eq},n,\text{min}} \leq [\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{eq},n,k} \leq [\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{eq},n,\text{max}}, \quad (96)$$

$$[\text{TOC}]_{n,\text{min}} \leq [\text{TOC}]_{n,k} \leq [\text{TOC}]_{n,\text{max}}, \quad (97)$$

$$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{n,\text{min}} \leq [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{n,k} \leq [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]_{n,\text{max}}, \quad (98)$$

$$[\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq},n,\text{min}} \leq [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq},n,k} \leq [\text{HOCl}]_{\text{eq},n,\text{max}}, \quad (99)$$

$$[\text{MnO}_4^-]_{n,\text{min}} \leq [\text{MnO}_4^-]_{n,k} \leq [\text{MnO}_4^-]_{n,\text{max}}, \quad (100)$$

$$[\text{K}^+]_{n,\text{min}} \leq [\text{K}^+]_{n,k} \leq [\text{K}^+]_{n,\text{max}}, \quad (101)$$

$$[\text{Cl}^-]_{n,\text{min}} \leq [\text{Cl}^-]_{n,k} \leq [\text{Cl}^-]_{n,\text{max}}, \quad (102)$$

$$[\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{eq},n,\text{min}} \leq [\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{eq},n,k} \leq [\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{eq},n,\text{max}}, \quad (103)$$

where $k = 0, \dots, N-1$. The minimum and maximum pH value is defined in each reaction volume $n \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{RV}}$:

$$\text{pH}_{n,\text{min}} \leq \text{pH}_{n,k} \leq \text{pH}_{n,\text{max}}. \quad (104)$$

It is important to define the flow limits of the carrier water for each reagent, as these represent the physical constraints of the injectors that dose the reagent for all times $k = 0, \dots, N-1$:

$$0 \leq q_{\text{KMnO}_4,k} \leq q_{\text{KMnO}_4,\text{max}}, \quad (105)$$

$$0 \leq q_{\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2,\text{RV}1,k} \leq q_{\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2,\text{RV}1,\text{max}}, \quad (106)$$

$$0 \leq q_{\text{Cl}_2,\text{RV}2,k} \leq q_{\text{Cl}_2,\text{RV}2,\text{max}}, \quad (107)$$

$$0 \leq q_{Al_2(SO_4)_3,k} \leq q_{Al_2(SO_4)_3,max}, \quad (108)$$

$$0 \leq q_{Ca(OH)_2,RV4,k} \leq q_{Ca(OH)_2,RV4,max}, \quad (109)$$

$$0 \leq q_{Cl_2,RV4,k} \leq q_{Cl_2,RV4,max}. \quad (110)$$

The equality constraint is imposed such that the concentration of each chemical component, i.e the state \mathbf{x} at the end of the prediction horizon is equal to the state at the beginning:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{n,0} = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{n,N} \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N}_{RV}. \quad (111)$$

Such constraint enables repetitive operation of the DWTP with periodicity equal to the length of the prediction horizon under the assumption of repetitive disturbance profile with the same periodicity. It is common to expect that disturbances evolve with daily period, and thus the prediction horizon is targeted to be one full day or 24 h. The optimal daily scheduling is carried out under the assumption of daily periodic disturbance variables.

The optimization problem is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\mathbf{z}} \mathcal{J} \\ & \text{subject to (42), (49), (92) – (111),} \end{aligned} \quad (112)$$

where the optimization variable \mathbf{z} is defined as

$$\mathbf{z} = [\mathbf{x}_0^T \quad \mathbf{u}_0^T \quad \mathbf{u}_1^T \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{u}_{N-1}^T]^T. \quad (113)$$

4. Sequential linear program for DWTP optimization

The methodology developed is targeted to improve the initial operation plan of the DWTP given with:

$$\mathbf{z}_0 = [\mathbf{x}_{0,0}^T \quad \mathbf{u}_{0,0}^T \quad \mathbf{u}_{1,0}^T \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{u}_{N-1,0}^T]^T. \quad (114)$$

At the initiation of the SLP procedure, the behaviour of the DWTP is simulated for several days with repeating control input (based on operators' recipes) and disturbance scenario until the diurnal harmonic operation is achieved. This is needed in order to obtain the repeatable operation of the plant which is a valid initial solution for the SLP, conforming also to the constraint $\mathbf{x}_0 = \mathbf{x}_N$. For these initial values the system model can be used in a system simulation set-up, relied on numerical integration procedures, to determine the response along the entire prediction horizon, i.e. the sequence of states along the prediction horizon ($\mathbf{x}_{0,0}, \mathbf{x}_{1,0}, \mathbf{x}_{2,0}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{N-1,0}, \mathbf{x}_{N,0}$).

4.1. DWTP solving for sensitivity analysis at an operation point

In this research, the fourth order Runge–Kutta method (RK4) [20] is used to numerically solve the system of differential Eqs. (33) along the entire prediction horizon. The linearization of the different elements of this optimization problem is performed around the sequence of operating points determined with \mathbf{z}_0 , obtained by using RK4 method of numerical integration. In the context of the DWTP model, each operating point determined with \mathbf{z}_0 at the time point $t = kT$ is defined by fixed states $\mathbf{x}_{k,0}$ and control inputs $\mathbf{u}_{k,0}$ along with predicted disturbances $\mathbf{d}_{k,0}$ defined with (34)–(41). Along with $\mathbf{x}_{k,0}$, $\mathbf{u}_{k,0}$ and $\mathbf{d}_{k,0}$, pH values in all reaction volumes of the DWTP are determined at discrete-time instants $k = 0, \dots, N - 1$:

$$(\text{pH}_{n,k})_{n \in \mathcal{N}_{RV}} = f_{OP}(\mathbf{x}_{k,0}, \mathbf{u}_{k,0}, \mathbf{d}_{k,0}), \quad (115)$$

where f_{OP} is a function of state, control inputs, and disturbances, which together determine the pH value in the reaction volumes.

For each discrete-time step k the plant sensitivity computation needs to be performed, which aims to assess how small changes in states, control inputs and disturbances affect the subsequent states evolution and the pH values in reaction volumes. In the following, to simplify the explanation the time index k in the variables is omitted. The changes

of states, i.e the concentrations of chemical compounds, changes of control inputs and disturbances for the DWTP can be written as:

$$[X]_n = [X]_{n,0} + \Delta[X]_n \quad n \in \mathcal{N}_{RV}, \quad (116)$$

$$q_{KMnO_4} = q_{KMnO_4,0} + \Delta q_{KMnO_4}, \quad (117)$$

$$q_{Ca(OH)_2,RV1} = q_{Ca(OH)_2,RV1,0} + \Delta q_{Ca(OH)_2,RV1}, \quad (118)$$

$$q_{Cl_2,RV2} = q_{Cl_2,RV2,0} + \Delta q_{Cl_2,RV2}, \quad (119)$$

$$q_{Al_2(SO_4)_3} = q_{Al_2(SO_4)_3,0} + \Delta q_{Al_2(SO_4)_3}, \quad (120)$$

$$q_{Ca(OH)_2,RV4} = q_{Ca(OH)_2,RV4,0} + \Delta q_{Ca(OH)_2,RV4}, \quad (121)$$

$$q_{Cl_2,RV4} = q_{Cl_2,RV4,0} + \Delta q_{Cl_2,RV4}, \quad (122)$$

$$[X]_{\text{raw}} = [X]_{\text{raw},0} + \Delta[X]_{\text{raw}}, \quad (123)$$

$$q_{DWTP_WDS} = q_{DWTP_WDS,0} + \Delta q_{DWTP_WDS}, \quad (124)$$

where $\Delta[X]_n$, Δq_{KMnO_4} , $\Delta q_{Ca(OH)_2,RV1}$, $\Delta q_{Cl_2,RV2}$, $\Delta q_{Al_2(SO_4)_3}$, $\Delta q_{Ca(OH)_2,RV4}$, $\Delta q_{Cl_2,RV4}$, $\Delta[X]_{\text{raw}}$ and Δq_{DWTP_WDS} denote perturbations in close vicinity of the operating point. Accordingly, small change of pH around the operating point is given by:

$$\text{pH}_n = \text{pH}_{n,0} + \Delta \text{pH}_n \quad n \in \mathcal{N}_{RV}, \quad (125)$$

where ΔpH_n expressed in (90) is a small change around the operating point.

From now on, small disturbance changes $\Delta \mathbf{d}$ will not be taken into account, as the raw water quality is considered with the same time profile once the concentrations and treated water demand are predicted with a certain prediction algorithm.

4.2. SLP formulation over the prediction horizon for the general reaction volume in the DWTP

Using the procedure described in 3.1, the expression of the dependence of a small change in the concentration of the chemical compounds in the reaction volume $n \in \mathcal{N}_{RV}$ at time instant k , is obtained:

$$\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{n,k+1} = \alpha_{n,k} \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{n,k} + \beta_{n,k} \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{n,k} + \gamma_{n,k} \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{n-1,k}, \quad (126)$$

where $\alpha_{n,k} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{x,n} \times n_{x,n}}$, $\beta_{n,k} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{x,n} \times n_{u,n}}$ and $\gamma_{n,k} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{x,n} \times n_{x,n-1}}$ are corresponding matrices of coefficients.

Now also all changes of states along the prediction horizon for $k = 0, 1, \dots, N$ can be expressed with respect to the change of the initial state $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{n,0}$ and the changes of the control input $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{n,k}$, $k = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1$, as follows [21]:

$$\Delta \mathbf{X}_n = \mathbf{A}_n \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{n,0} + \mathbf{B}_n \Delta \mathbf{U}_n + \mathbf{C}_n \Delta \mathbf{R}_n, \quad (127)$$

$$\mathbf{A}_n = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \alpha_{n,0} \\ \alpha_{n,0} \alpha_{n,1} \\ \vdots \\ \prod_{i=0}^{N-1} \alpha_{n,i} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (128)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_n = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \beta_{n,0} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \alpha_{n,1} \beta_{n,0} & \beta_{n,1} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{B}_{\text{end},n,0} & \mathbf{B}_{\text{end},n,1} & \cdots & \mathbf{B}_{\text{end},n,N-1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (129)$$

where $\mathbf{B}_{\text{end},n,j}$ for matrix column index $j = 0, \dots, N - 1$ is defined as:

$$\mathbf{B}_{\text{end},n,j} = \left(\prod_{i=1}^{N-1-j} \alpha_{n,i} \right) \beta_{n,j}. \quad (130)$$

The matrix \mathbf{C}_n is defined as:

$$\mathbf{C}_n = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \gamma_{n,0} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ \alpha_{n,1}\gamma_{n,0} & \gamma_{n,1} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}_{\text{end},n,0} & \mathbf{C}_{\text{end},n,1} & \cdots & \mathbf{C}_{\text{end},n,N-1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (131)$$

where $\mathbf{C}_{\text{end},n,j}$ for matrix column index $j = 0, \dots, N-1$ is defined as:

$$\mathbf{C}_{\text{end},n,j} = \left(\prod_{i=1}^{N-1-j} \alpha_{n,i} \right) \gamma_{n,j}. \quad (132)$$

The changes of states and control inputs $\Delta\mathbf{X}_n$, $\Delta\mathbf{U}_n$ and $\Delta\mathbf{R}_n$ for the specific reaction volume $n \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{RV}}$ are defined as follows:

$$\Delta\mathbf{X}_n = \left[\Delta\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{n,0}^T, \Delta\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{n,1}^T, \dots, \Delta\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{n,N}^T \right]^T, \quad (133)$$

$$\Delta\mathbf{U}_n = \left[\Delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{n,0}^T, \Delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{n,1}^T, \dots, \Delta\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{n,N-1}^T \right]^T, \quad (134)$$

$$\Delta\mathbf{R}_n = \left[\Delta\mathbf{X}_1^T, \Delta\mathbf{X}_2^T, \dots, \Delta\mathbf{X}_{n-1}^T, \Delta\mathbf{U}_1^T, \Delta\mathbf{U}_2^T, \dots, \Delta\mathbf{U}_{n-1}^T \right]^T. \quad (135)$$

Furthermore, for the n th reaction volume, the output changes $\Delta\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_n$ – assigned to variable $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_n$ as defined in (43) – can also be expressed along the prediction horizon with respect to $\Delta\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{n,0}$ and $\Delta\mathbf{U}_{n,0}$. Combining the matrix of coefficients from (90) and (127) yields the matrices \mathbf{E}_n and \mathbf{F}_n that relate $\Delta\mathbf{Y}_n$ to $\Delta\mathbf{X}_n$ and $\Delta\mathbf{U}_n$:

$$\Delta\mathbf{Y}_n = \mathbf{E}_n \Delta\mathbf{X}_n + \mathbf{F}_n \Delta\mathbf{U}_n, \quad (136)$$

where $\Delta\mathbf{Y}_n$ is defined as:

$$\Delta\mathbf{Y}_n = \left[\Delta\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{n,0}^T, \Delta\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{n,1}^T, \dots, \Delta\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{n,N}^T \right]^T. \quad (137)$$

Substituting (127) into (136) yields the final expression

$$\Delta\mathbf{Y}_n = \mathbf{E}_n \mathbf{A}_n \Delta\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{n,0} + (\mathbf{E}_n \mathbf{B}_n + \mathbf{F}_n) \Delta\mathbf{U}_n + \mathbf{E}_n \mathbf{C}_n \Delta\mathbf{R}_n. \quad (138)$$

In order to obtain the formulation of a Linear Program (LP) for optimizing $\Delta\mathbf{x}_0$ and $\Delta\mathbf{U}$, it is necessary first to express the cost function with respect to the change of the optimization variable $\Delta\mathbf{z}$:

$$\mathcal{J} = \mathbf{W} \Delta\mathbf{z} + \mathcal{J}_0, \quad (139)$$

where \mathbf{W} and \mathcal{J}_0 are respectively:

$$\mathbf{W} = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \mathbf{G}_{1,k} + \mathbf{G}_{2,k} + \mathbf{G}_{3,k} + \mathbf{G}_{4,k}, \quad (140)$$

$$\mathcal{J}_0 = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} c_{1,k} + c_{2,k} + c_{3,k} + c_{4,k}. \quad (141)$$

where $\mathbf{G}_{n,k} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_x + N \cdot n_u) \times (n_x + N \cdot n_u)}$, $c_{n,k} \in \mathbb{R}$, $k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$ are derived from (91) and the small change of the optimization variable $\Delta\mathbf{z}$ for the considered DWTP is defined as

$$\Delta\mathbf{z} = \left[\Delta\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{1,0}^T, \Delta\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{2,0}^T, \Delta\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{3,0}^T, \Delta\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{4,0}^T, \Delta\mathbf{U}_1^T, \Delta\mathbf{U}_2^T, \Delta\mathbf{U}_3^T, \Delta\mathbf{U}_4^T \right]^T. \quad (142)$$

Furthermore, the constraints for the concentrations in the n th reaction volume can be expressed by merging expressions (45), (92)–(103), (116) and (127):

$$\mathbf{X}_{n,\min} \leq \mathbf{X}_{n,k,0} + \mathbf{V}_k (\mathbf{A}_n \Delta\mathbf{x}_{n,0} + \mathbf{B}_n \Delta\mathbf{U}_n + \mathbf{C}_n \Delta\mathbf{R}_n) \leq \mathbf{X}_{n,\max}, \quad (143)$$

where $n \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{RV}}$, $\mathbf{X}_{n,k,0}$ represents all concentrations at the operating point at discrete-time step k , $\mathbf{X}_{n,\min}$ and $\mathbf{X}_{n,\max}$ are the minimum and maximum allowed concentrations of all chemical compounds, respectively; and \mathbf{V}_k is a selection matrix that extracts all concentrations at discrete-time step k for the n th reaction volume. The constraints (104)–(111) can be expressed by using an analogous procedure. Additionally, limiting small changes in states and control inputs is necessary to ensure the accuracy of linearization at all time steps $k = 0, \dots, N-1$:

$$-\Delta\mathbf{X}_{\min} \leq \Delta\mathbf{x}_k \leq \Delta\mathbf{X}_{\max}, \quad (144)$$

$$-\Delta\mathbf{U}_{\min} \leq \Delta\mathbf{u}_k \leq \Delta\mathbf{U}_{\max}, \quad (145)$$

where $\Delta\mathbf{X}_{\min}$ and $\Delta\mathbf{X}_{\max}$ are the vectors of the minimum and maximum allowed small changes in state, that is small changes in concentrations in all the reaction volumes throughout the prediction horizon, while $\Delta\mathbf{U}_{\min}$ and $\Delta\mathbf{U}_{\max}$ are the vectors of the minimum and maximum allowed small changes in control inputs, i.e. small changes in inputs flows of prepared solutions of chemicals. As the DWTP model is nonlinear, solving the optimization problem is performed iteratively by linearizing the model using the Sequential Linear Programming (SLP) procedure. The limits of small changes were selected to ensure that, during a series of simulations with different raw water quality during the day and flow profile dictated by the WDS, the solution remained feasible in all iterations. This indicates that the changes in the linearized model are small enough to closely follow the nonlinear model with high accuracy.

Due to additional constraints and submodels introduced for discrete-time modelling of fast chemical reactions, as explained in detail in Section 3.1, optimization using SLP is performed by applying a linearized model within the currently valid full-dimensional region for a specific fast chemical reaction. Each iteration of the linear program in SLP does not allow exiting this region but only progresses to its boundary. Then, depending on which boundary is reached, the corresponding constraint is inverted in the next iteration, forcing the next iteration to be performed in the new region. The process then continues in an analogous manner. This linearized representation can then be used to solve the problem for a small change in the initial conditions and control inputs, as a linear program (LP). The LP for the DWTP is derived by integrating all the previously described constraints. It can be expressed as follows:

$$\min_{\Delta\mathbf{z}} \mathcal{J} = \min_{\Delta\mathbf{z}} (\mathbf{W} \Delta\mathbf{z} + \mathcal{J}_0) \quad (146)$$

$$\text{subject to:} \quad (147)$$

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{ineq}} \Delta\mathbf{z} \leq \mathbf{b}_{\text{ineq}},$$

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{eq}} \Delta\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{b}_{\text{eq}}, \quad (148)$$

where \mathbf{A}_{ineq} is the coefficient matrix of all previously derived inequality constraints along the prediction horizon, \mathbf{b}_{ineq} is the right-hand-side vector associated with the corresponding inequality constraints, \mathbf{A}_{eq} is the coefficient matrix of all previously derived equality constraints along the prediction horizon and \mathbf{b}_{eq} is the right-hand-side vector associated with the corresponding equality constraints along the prediction horizon.

The LP can be solved by using one of the linear optimization solvers, leading to locally optimal changes

$$\Delta\mathbf{z}_0^* = \left[(\Delta\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_0^*)^T \quad (\Delta\mathbf{u}_0^*)^T \quad (\Delta\mathbf{u}_1^*)^T \quad \cdots \quad (\Delta\mathbf{u}_{N-1}^*)^T \right]^T, \quad (149)$$

and finally, the improved optimization variable is obtained as

$$\mathbf{z}_1 = \mathbf{z}_0 + \Delta\mathbf{z}_0^*. \quad (150)$$

The optimization variable \mathbf{z}_1 is used as the initial point for the next iteration of the optimization in the SLP procedure. In the j th iteration of the SLP ($j = 1, 2, \dots$) the optimization variable \mathbf{z}_j is obtained

$$\mathbf{z}_j = \mathbf{z}_{j-1} + \Delta\mathbf{z}_{j-1}^*. \quad (151)$$

The sequence of SLP iterations can be stopped once the decrease in the optimal cost falls below a certain threshold for several iterations, or once the time allowed for computation has elapsed. The solution obtained in the last iteration step \mathcal{S}_{\max} , $\mathbf{z}_{\mathcal{S}_{\max}}$, is the improvement, potentially a substantial one, compared to the initial plan of running the system represented with \mathbf{z}_0 .

Fig. 2. The flow at the outlet of the fourth reaction volume.

Fig. 3. Comparison between the optimized potassium permanganate solution input flow profile and the profile generated from the baseline operation in RV1.

5. Case study in Spain and results

Previously introduced algorithm was validated through a simulation using the actual parameters of a real DWTP in a city in Spain, as shown in Fig. 1 and described in more detail in Section 2. A prediction horizon of 24 h is selected, based on the dynamics of the plant, ability to well predict all disturbance profiles within that time, computational complexity and comfort for the plant operators. Total capacity of the entire plant is 60,000 m³/d. The amounts of the reaction volumes are as follows: $V_1 = 500$ m³, $V_2 = 300$ m³, $V_3 = 1620$ m³, $V_4 = 375$ m³. The chlorine decay constant is $k_d = 0.00059$ s⁻¹. Semi-empirical coefficients additionally tuned in Edwards model are as follows [18]: $\lambda_1 = 300$, $\lambda_2 = -68.2$, $\lambda_3 = 5.0$, $K_1 = -0.075$ mg m/L, $K_2 = 0.56$, $b_{\text{langmuir}} = 0.147$ L/mg. Baseline operation is obtained using recipe-based setup. The recipes determine how much chemicals needs to be dosed depending on the concentrations of manganese, iron and TOC in the raw water inflow, and also depending on the water intake into the DWTP q_{raw} . These recipes are currently applied in operation of the DWTP by the plant operators.

The daily disturbance scenario for the DWTP in this case study is described in the sequel. At the moment $t = 5$ h, the initial concentration of manganese $[\text{Mn}^{2+}]_{\text{raw}}$ in the raw water, which is 0.543 mg/L, increases by 15%. Also, the initial iron concentration $[\text{Fe}^{2+}]_{\text{raw}}$, which is 0.308 mg/L, increases by 20% at $t = 12.5$ h. The concentration of equivalent calcium $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{eq,raw}}$ in the raw water inflow is 41 mg/L, while the concentration of equivalent carbonic acid $[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]_{\text{eq,raw}}$ is 175 mg/L.

Table 5

The concentrations of reagents in their corresponding dosing solutions and prices per kilogram of chemical reagents.

Reagent	Concentration (g/L)	Price (EUR/kg)
KMnO ₄	15	18.67
Ca(OH) ₂	1.73	0.159
Cl ₂	3.2	1.46
Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	1330	2

Finally, the concentrations of equivalent magnesium $[\text{Mg}^{2+}]_{\text{eq,raw}}$ and total organic carbon $[\text{TOC}]_{\text{raw}}$ are 4.5 mg/L and 6.12 mg/L, respectively. All other chemicals are not present in raw water. The flow at the outlet of the last reaction volume dictated by the WDS is shown in Fig. 2. This flow was obtained by optimizing the WDS segment of the same city in Spain [22], with an additional constraint introduced as follows:

$$300 \left(\frac{\text{L}}{\text{s}} \right) \leq q_{\text{DWTP,WDS},k} \leq 700 \left(\frac{\text{L}}{\text{s}} \right). \quad (152)$$

The price and concentration of chemicals that are dosed in the DWTP are shown in Table 5.

5.1. SLP operation of the entire DWTP

The input flow profiles of potassium permanganate and lime into the first reaction volume obtained from the baseline operation and the SLP procedure are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively. The

Fig. 4. Comparison between the optimized lime input flow profile and the profile generated from the baseline operation in RV1.

Fig. 5. The concentrations $[K^+]$, $[HOCl]_{eq}$, $[Mn^{2+}]$, $[Fe^{2+}]$, $[Ca^{2+}]_{eq}$, $[H_2CO_3]_{eq}$ in RV1 obtained from the baseline operation and the SLP procedure.

concentrations of all the significant chemical elements for the first reaction volume are shown in Fig. 5, while the pH value at the output of the first reaction volume is shown in Fig. 6. As shown in Fig. 3, potassium permanganate usage is reduced compared to the baseline operation, since it is more expensive than chlorine, which offsets this

reduction in the second reaction volume. Although the lime dosage profile from the SLP procedure is lower than in the baseline operation, the pH at the outlet of the first reaction volume remains within the operator-specified limits which is visible in Fig. 6. Furthermore, the input flow profiles of chlorine gas into the second reaction volume

Fig. 6. The pH value at the output of the first reaction volume.

Fig. 7. Comparison between the optimized chlorine gas solution input flow profile and the profile generated from the baseline operation in RV2.

are shown in Fig. 7, while the concentrations of significant chemical elements in the second reaction volume, are shown in Fig. 8. The pH value at the output of the second reaction volume is shown in Fig. 9. As shown in Fig. 7, there is increased use of chlorine gas, as previously mentioned. At the outlet of the second reaction volume, the concentrations of iron and manganese are reduced, which is evident in Fig. 8. Prior to the coagulation process occurring in the third reaction volume, Fig. 9 shows that the pH value remains within the permissible

limits necessary for an effective coagulation process. The input flow profile of aluminium sulphate into the third reaction volume is shown in Fig. 10. The concentrations of significant chemical elements in the third reaction volume, are shown in Fig. 11 and the pH value at the output of the third reaction volume is shown in Fig. 12. Fig. 10 shows a reduced use of aluminium sulphate, while Fig. 11 confirms that the TOC concentration remains within the maximum allowable limit. Optimized pH in RV2 enables smaller solubility of aluminium in water and thus

Fig. 8. The concentrations $[Mn^{2+}]$, $[Fe^{2+}]$, $[K^+]$, $[HOCl]_{eq}$, $[Cl^-]$, $[SO_4^{2-}]$ in RV2 obtained from the baseline operation and the SLP procedure.

Fig. 9. The pH value at the output of the second reaction volume.

Fig. 10. Comparison between the optimized aluminium sulphate solution input flow profile and the profile generated from the baseline operation.

Fig. 11. The concentrations of $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$, $[\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{eq}}$, $[\text{TOC}]$, $[\text{Mg}^{2+}]_{\text{eq}}$, $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{eq}}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3]_{\text{eq}}$ in RV3 obtained from the baseline operation and the SLP procedure.

Fig. 12. The pH value at the output of the third reaction volume.

Fig. 13. Comparison between the optimized lime input flow profile and the profile generated from the baseline operation in RV4.

more effective coagulation. In this way also a smaller concentration of dissolved aluminium in water reduces potential secondary health risks for the population. Further, exaggerated introduction of the coagulant in water performed by classical recipes, consumes H_2CO_3 and its species (later evident in Figs. 11 and 15) which are actually excellent pH buffers — this requires later higher lime addition to recover the pH, and still it will be visible in the last reaction volume that pH response is

very dynamic for the classical way of operation. The input flow profiles of lime and chlorine gas into the fourth reaction volume obtained from the baseline operation and the SLP procedure are shown in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14 respectively. Concentrations of all considered chemical elements in the fourth reaction volume, that is at the DWTP outlet are shown in Figs. 15 and 16. The pH value at the output of the fourth reaction volume is shown in Fig. 17. Additionally, a higher lime

Fig. 14. Comparison between the optimized chlorine gas input flow profile and the profile generated from the baseline operation in RV4.

Fig. 15. The concentrations of $[MnO_4^-]$, $[Al^{3+}]_{eq}$, $[Mn^{2+}]$, $[Fe^{2+}]$, $[Ca^{2+}]_{eq}$, $[H_2CO_3]_{eq}$ in RV4 obtained from the baseline operation and the SLP procedure.

Fig. 16. The concentrations of $[K^+]$, $[HOCl]_{eq}$, $[TOC]$, $[Mg^{2+}]_{eq}$, $[Cl^-]$, $[SO_4^{2-}]$ in RV4 obtained from the baseline operation and the SLP procedure.

Fig. 17. The pH value at the output of the fourth reaction volume.

Fig. 18. Total cost of daily operation of the DWTP through iterations of the SLP optimization procedure.

Table 6

Comparison of the total daily chemical dosing volumes.

Operation	KMnO ₄ [L]	Ca(OH) ₂ , RV1 [L]	Cl ₂ , RV2 [L]	Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ [L]	Ca(OH) ₂ , RV4 [L]	Cl ₂ , RV4 [L]
Baseline	2361	78 570	52 259	2696	146 012	20 952
Optimal	78	50 208	63 220	1538	26 140	16 671

Table 7

Cost comparison of individual chemical solution dosage.

Operation	KMnO ₄ [EUR]	Ca(OH) ₂ , RV1 [EUR]	Cl ₂ , RV2 [EUR]	Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ [EUR]	Ca(OH) ₂ , RV4 [EUR]	Cl ₂ , RV4 [EUR]
Baseline	650.23	21.39	240.22	7055.75	39.54	96.88
Optimal	21.31	13.97	291.33	4025.06	7.13	77.26

Table 8

Total cost comparison.

Operation	Total cost [EUR]	Relative savings
Baseline	8104.00	
Optimal	4435.75	45.26%

addition with static recipes is required because the pH is lowered by excess aluminium, and H₂CO₃ is deficient due to the high coagulant dose used in RV3.

Total cost of daily operation of the DWTP through iterations of the optimization procedure is shown in Fig. 18. The cost value at iteration zero represents the cost associated with the baseline operation. Table 6 presents a comparison of the total daily chemical dosing volumes, demonstrating the use of cheaper chemicals in place of more expensive ones. Cost comparison of individual chemical solutions dosages is shown in Table 7. Finally, the comparison of total costs is shown in Table 8. The relative total cost savings using the SLP optimization procedure compared to the baseline operation is 45.26%. They are achieved due to the optimal operation of the entire plant, where the system dynamics are fully known. This allows for the use of cheaper chlorine gas in place of potassium permanganate and a reduction in the dosage of aluminium sulphate conversely to a recipe-based operation. In Figs. 15, 16 and 17, which show the output from the fourth reaction volume, it can be seen that by the end of the SLP procedure, the stringent water quality standards are met. Specifically, the concentrations of manganese and iron are kept within their maximum allowable limits, and the pH value remains within the defined limits. The constraint on the minimum concentration of [HOCl]_{eq} is also satisfied, as well as the equality constraint described by expression (111) that allows the optimized operation to be repeatedly executable day by day, under the

assumption of periodic profile of daily disturbances. The optimization procedure was performed on an ARM-based Apple M4 Max SoC with 14 CPU and 32 GPU cores, while the RAM size is 36 GB. Maximum CPU clock rate is 4.51 GHz. Python, in which the program is executed, is also ARM-based. The execution time for the whole optimization procedure including all the iterations shown is 13.1 minutes. Due to the strict stopping criterion of the SLP procedure – defined as a change in the cost function of less than 10⁻⁵ EUR between iterations – a large number of iterations is required. As shown in Fig. 18, convergence becomes clearly visible around iteration 100, where the change in the cost function becomes very small. The corresponding execution time up to this iteration is 6.1 min. Such computation time achieved allows the procedure to be extended towards autonomous model predictive control, with DWTP operators taking a more relaxed supervisory role compared to their current human-in-the-loop role.

5.2. Sensitivity to disturbance profile and initial solution

Sensitivity of the SLP-based optimization procedure is examined with respect to variations in both external disturbances and initial solution \mathbf{z}_0 . The analysis is carried out by introducing small perturbations and observing the resulting changes in the optimization outcomes.

A small change in the system disturbance is introduced by first increasing and then decreasing the water flow at the DWTP outlet by 1%. The optimization procedure is then re-applied under each perturbed scenario, and the results are compared to those of the nominal case. For the sake of clarity of the article, the comparison is shown only for the dosage of aluminium sulphate. Comparison of aluminium sulphate dosing profiles under a 1% increase and decrease in water flow at the DWTP outlet is shown in Fig. 19. In the legend of Fig. 19, the letter 'D' denotes a disturbance. Furthermore, comparison of the total cost of

Fig. 19. Comparison of aluminium sulphate dosing profiles under a 1% increase and decrease in disturbance.

Fig. 20. Comparison of the total cost of daily operation of the DWTP through iterations of the SLP optimization procedure for increased and decreased disturbance.

daily operation of the DWTP through iterations of the SLP optimization procedure for increased and decreased disturbance is shown in Fig. 20. It is observed that, despite the $\pm 1\%$ changes in disturbance values, the optimization process produced control profiles that satisfied all imposed constraints. Additionally, The relative savings changed slightly. For the case of increasing disturbance, they decreased to 44.88%, while for decreasing disturbance, they increased to 45.65%. This indicates that the cost-effectiveness of the optimization procedure is not affected significantly by small variations in the input disturbances.

To evaluate sensitivity to the initial conditions, the recipes for the dosages of the prepared solutions are increased and then decreased by 1%. The optimization is then repeated for each modified scenario. Comparison of the aluminium sulphate dosing profiles across SLP iterations for both scenarios is shown in Fig. 21. In the legend of the figure, the letter 'R' denotes recipes. It is found that the process variables evolved slightly differently during the early iterations, but the same final concentrations are reached as in the unperturbed case. Constraint satisfaction was preserved throughout the entire time horizon. These observations suggest that small changes in initial conditions do not significantly affect the final outcome of the optimization. This can be

confirmed by Fig. 22 which shows the comparison of the total cost of daily operation of the DWTP through iterations of the SLP optimization procedure for increased and decreased recipes. That is, the total cost at the end of the SLP procedure remains equal to the nominal total cost, even when the recipes are increased or decreased by 1%.

This sensitivity analysis indicates that the proposed SLP-based optimization procedure behaves consistently when subjected to small variations in both, system disturbance and initial conditions.

5.3. Discussion on implementation and robustness

In the presence of non-perfect knowledge of the disturbance profile along the prediction horizon as well as due to non-perfect model of the DWTP, it is also important to discuss how to compensate for their influence with further extension of the introduced optimization. An elementary way to increase robustness is to introduce more frequent than daily optimization feedback, as presumed with the operator decision support setup. In this way the control actions can be adapted regularly to non-perfect models and predictions. This leads to receding horizon control that seems to be viable according to the achieved

Fig. 21. Comparison of aluminium sulphate dosing profiles through iterations of SLP optimization procedure under a 1% increase and decrease in recipes.

Fig. 22. Comparison of the total cost of daily operation of the DWTP through iterations of the SLP optimization procedure for increased and decreased recipes.

computation times required for a single optimization, determined in this section. Real-time feedback in case of DWTPs regularly involves only a portion of chemicals concentrations that are part of the model state and disturbance vector — that is why also a state and disturbance estimator would have to accompany the implementation.

Having the optimal control problem formulated in the form of a SLP for the sequence of linearized dynamic plant models along the prediction horizon, there are several robust control methodologies available to increase the computed optimal control sequence robustness to uncertain predictions of disturbances — i.e. of raw water composition and the fresh water consumption over time. Additional uncertainties come from the imperfect model and not accurately known state estimates. These approaches are: min-max optimization, stochastic optimization, scenario-based and tube-based. They all of course come at the cost of additional computational complexity, and require that the model is linearized also with respect to small changes in disturbance.

Optimization in the case of robust optimal control problems is usually performed over control policies with taken into account the presumption that the control inputs at a certain time-point of the

prediction horizon can counteract the past realizations of disturbances relative to that time-point. Min-max optimal control problem for the case of changing linear models requires a sequence of multi-parametric linear programs to be solved on-line, which is a computationally prohibitive procedure, especially in the context of sequential linear programming where its each iteration would require a sequence of multi-parametric programs. In stochastic optimal control problems constraints are posed in a probabilistic form where the uncertainty in disturbance realization is usually assumed in a Gaussian form and then propagated with linear models over the prediction horizon. Scenario-based approach requires to generate a sequence of disturbance realization scenarios around a nominal disturbance trajectory and then further it requires that the constraints are satisfied for all of them. Tube-based optimal control problem accounts for the disturbance actions across the prediction horizon which are adding-up and thus tightening the constraints and requires to effectively indent constraints on the state variables through the prediction horizon.

6. Conclusion

This paper introduces an optimization procedure based on sequential linear programming for drinking water treatment plants (DWTPs). It presents a detailed physicochemical model for a general reaction volume of a DWTP and thoroughly explains the DWTP model time discretization and linearization procedure. Unlike previous approaches all reaction volumes are encompassed in a single procedure which provides the opportunity to optimize the overall plant performance. The operational costs of the DWTP are introduced, which are locally minimized while meeting all requirements. The procedure was validated on a DWTP in a city in Spain. The savings are substantial, indicating significant economical potential for the implementation of the described procedure on various DWTPs. The achieved computation complexity and computation time allow to extend the introduced procedure towards autonomous model predictive control of the entire DWTP.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Blaž Korotaj: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Hrvoje Novak:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Nikola Hure:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Victoria Álvarez Uliarte:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Mario Vašak:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix. State-space model variables and parameters description

Tables A.9 and A.10 show description of the state-space model variables and parameters.

Table A.9

Description of state-space model variables and subscripts.

	Variable	Description	Units
Sets	\mathcal{N}_{RV}	Set of indices of reaction volumes (RVs)	–
	n	Indices from the set of indices \mathcal{N}_{RV}	–
	$[X]_{eq}$	Subscript 'eq' denotes the total concentration of all species of the corresponding chemical element X (i.e. equivalent)	mol/L
Subscripts	$q_{X,RV1}$	Subscript 'RV' denotes the reaction volume	L/s
	$[X]_{in}$	The subscript 'in' in $[X]_{in}$ denotes the concentration of the chemical compound X that is dissolved in its corresponding input stream into the reaction volume	mol/L
	q_{prv}	Subscript 'prv' denotes the previous reaction volume	L/s
	$q_{in,total}$	Subscript 'total' represents the combined contribution of the dosed solutions and of the previous reaction volume	L/s
	k	Integer multiple of the sampling time	–
States	$[MnO_4^-]_{eq,n}$, $[Cl^-]_{in}$, $[HOCl]_{eq,n}$, $[Mn^{2+}]_{eq,n}$, $[Fe^{2+}]_{eq,n}$, $[Ca^{2+}]_{eq,n}$, $[Mg^{2+}]_{eq,n}$, $[H_2CO_3]_{eq,n}$, $[K^+]_{eq,n}$, $[TOC]_{eq,n}$, $[Al^{3+}]_{eq,n}$, $[SO_4^{2-}]_{eq,n}$	Concentrations in reaction volume $n \in \mathcal{N}_{RV}$ of permanganate, chloride ion, total free chlorine, manganese, iron, equivalent calcium, equivalent magnesium, equivalent carbonic acid, potassium, total organic carbon, equivalent aluminium, sulphate, respectively	mol/L
Inputs	q_{KMnO_4} , $q_{Ca(OH)_2,RV1}$, $q_{Cl_2,RV2}$, $q_{Al_2(SO_4)_3}$, $q_{Ca(OH)_2,RV4}$, $q_{Cl_2,RV4}$	(Reference) flows of input water in which the corresponding reagents (potassium permanganate, lime in RV1, chlorine gas in RV2, aluminium sulphate, lime in RV4 and chlorine gas in RV4) are dissolved	L/s
Disturbances	$[Mn^{2+}]_{raw}$, $[Fe^{2+}]_{raw}$, $[H_2CO_3]_{eq,raw}$, $[Mg^{2+}]_{eq,raw}$, $[Ca^{2+}]_{eq,raw}$, $[TOC]_{raw}$, $[SO_4^{2-}]_{raw}$, $[HOCl]_{eq,raw}$, $[MnO_4^-]_{raw}$, $[K^+]_{raw}$, $[Cl^-]_{raw}$, $[Al^{3+}]_{raw}$, $q_{DWTP,WDS}$	Concentrations of raw water elements (manganese, iron, equivalent carbonic acid, equivalent magnesium, equivalent calcium, total organic carbon, sulphate, total free chlorine, permanganate, potassium, chloride ion, aluminium, respectively) at the inlet to the first reaction volume Water intake into the WDS	mol/L L/s
Outputs	$\tilde{x}_{n,k}$	Concentrations of the chemical elements at the outlet of the reaction volume $n \in \mathcal{N}_{RV}$ at time instant k	mol/L
	$pH_{n,k}$	pH value at the outlet of the reaction volume $n \in \mathcal{N}_{RV}$ at time instant k	–

Table A.10
Description of parameters in the DWTP model.

	Variable	Description	Units
Parameters	K_{S0}	Equilibrium constant of Al^{3+} with amorphous aluminium hydroxide $Al(OH)_3(s)$	L^2/mol^2
	K_{S1}	Equilibrium constant of $Al(OH)^{2+}$ with amorphous aluminium hydroxide $Al(OH)_3(s)$	L/mol
	K_{S2}	Equilibrium constant of $Al(OH)_2^+$ with amorphous aluminium hydroxide $Al(OH)_3(s)$	–
	K_{S3}	Equilibrium constant of $Al(OH)_3^0$ with amorphous aluminium hydroxide $Al(OH)_3(s)$	L/mol
	K_{S4}	Equilibrium constant of $Al(OH)_4^-$ with amorphous aluminium hydroxide $Al(OH)_3(s)$	mol^2/L^2
	k_d	Chlorine decay constant	1/s
	V	Size of the reaction volume	L
	k_w	Water dissociation constant	mol^2/L^2
	c_{avg}	Average charge of the dissolved aluminium species at pH value 7	–
	P_{KMnO_4}	Price of potassium permanganate	EUR/kg
	$P_{Ca(OH)_2}$	Price of lime	EUR/kg
	P_{Cl_2}	Price of chlorine gas	EUR/kg
	$P_{Al_2(SO_4)_3}$	Price of aluminium sulphate	EUR/kg
	M_{KMnO_4}	Molar mass of potassium permanganate	kg/mol
	$M_{Ca(OH)_2}$	Molar mass of lime	kg/mol
M_{Cl_2}	Molar mass of chlorine gas	kg/mol	
$M_{Al_2(SO_4)_3}$	Molar mass of aluminium sulphate	kg/mol	
Edwards model	K_1	Empirical constant in expression for non-adsorbable TOC	mg m/L
	K_2	Empirical constant in expression for non-adsorbable TOC	–
	$b_{langmuir}$	Langmuir equilibrium constant	L/mg
	λ_1	Empirical constant in expression for total adsorbent capacity at monolayer coverage	–
empirical constants	λ_2	Empirical constant in expression for total adsorbent capacity at monolayer coverage	–
	λ_3	Empirical constant in expression for total adsorbent capacity at monolayer coverage	–

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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